

ASSESSING GRADE 9 STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN MATHEMATICS 8: BASIS FOR MATH TEACHER'S ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to assess the competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 at Sto Niño High School in the academic year 2023-2024. The researchers used quantitative research with descriptive statistics. The selection technique employed by the researchers was purposive sampling because the participants were targeted and fitted into the study. A 5-point Likert scale was utilized with a range that constitutes verbal description to describe the competence level of Grade 9 students in the said competencies. Moreover, using weighted means, the researchers were able to calculate the dataset and use it to describe the participants' competence level in each quarter. The results revealed that in the first and second quarters, the students were found to be slightly competent. Moreover, in the third quarter, students demonstrated moderate competence. On the other hand, in the last quarter, the students were competent in one competency. Thus, the general competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 was moderately competent. The results were substantiated by participants' sentiments regarding the reasons that contributed to their competence. These included a lack of resources, students' lack of interest, and teachers' pedagogical knowledge and approaches. This study suggests that mathematics teachers should be innovative and resourceful in presenting lessons and implementing enhancement programs to help learners enhance their least learned competencies. Furthermore, the researchers recommend that future researchers use a correlation method using variables that may explain the association and relationship between students' competence in mathematics.

Keywords: *Quantitative Research, Descriptive Statistics, Grade 9 competence in Mathematics 8, Lack of Resources, Students' Attitude and Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Approach*

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of education, the effectiveness of the curriculum and instructional strategies hinges significantly on students' proficiency in mathematics throughout the academic term. The mastery of mathematical concepts, ranging from algebra to problem-solving, serves as a cornerstone for academic success across various disciplines. Globally, mathematics is considered one of the most significant disciplines taught in schools. A country's socioeconomic development is greatly aided by scientific and technological knowledge (Chand et al., 2021). Moreover, Math is a necessary component of daily life and can be used to resolve real-world issues. Math abilities may improve our lives in a variety of ways, from calculating a grocery store sale discount to determining the distance between the two sites. Math proficiency enables us to assess data, make defensible decisions, and effectively solve real-world issues. These are practical abilities that can be used in everyday life and in academic contexts. One may comprehend financial statements, estimate costs, and choose the most efficient commuting route when one possesses the necessary mathematical skills. Math does not have to be difficult; anyone can become more practical and benefit from its application by understanding how to apply fundamental mathematical concepts to everyday life (Team and Team, 2023). Additionally, mathematics is essential to human reasoning and thought processes to understand the world and us. Logical reasoning and mental rigor are encouraged by mathematics, which also offers an efficient method of developing mental discipline (The Role of Mathematics in the Overall Curriculum, International Mathematical Union (IMU), n.d.).

Teachers play a crucial role in assessing students' competencies in mathematics, identifying strengths and weaknesses, and creating tailored intervention plans to enhance their mathematical abilities. By leveraging insights from comprehensive assessments, educators can foster a conducive learning environment that promotes deeper understanding and practical application of mathematical principles, empowering students for their academic and professional futures. However, mathematics has long been regarded as a challenging subject for many students, often viewed as their Achilles heel due to its perceived complexity. This widespread sentiment towards mathematics has led to general disinterest and difficulties in comprehension and analysis among learners. Recognizing this issue, educators are increasingly exploring ways to bridge this gap and make mathematics more accessible and engaging. In this pursuit, the brightest minds in mathematics are devising innovative solutions that aim to alleviate these challenges without compromising the integrity of the curriculum or fundamental principles of the subject (ipl.org, 2021). In addition, math frequently comprises multistep issues, for which pupils must be able to carry out numerous sequential stages to discover a solution. This is one of the reasons math is difficult to learn. This necessitates maintaining an active concentration in the current study. Students frequently become sidetracked and lose

attention when learning difficult mathematical methods. Because of this, they can overlook crucial steps in the problem-solving process and subsequently find it difficult to solve arithmetic issues on their own. This problem may arise due to several factors, including a lack of resources, teachers' pedagogy, and students' interest. This was substantiated by Sirajo and Abdullahi (2023). The study's findings demonstrate that students' ability to learn mathematics is influenced by the accessibility and use of educational materials. The utilization of teaching tools and stimulation of students' senses sparked interest in the subject matter. Students perform better in mathematics when the application of instructional materials is prioritized in the classroom. One significant aspect that affects how mathematics is taught and learned in schools is the availability of instructional resources. Moreover, a lack of devices, such as laptops, cellphones, and Internet access, might prevent students from completing their projects and assignments, which negatively impacts their academic achievement (Torres, 2024).

Teachers' pedagogy and content knowledge affect learners' academic performance. The most important function in reflecting students' interests and talents is played by math teachers, who also provide conceptual understanding through strong pedagogical content knowledge (PCK). According to the study of Sakaria et al. (2023), there is a strong need to support the math teachers we currently have to increase their PCK levels and strengthen their competencies by closing this gap. Aside from a lack of resources and teachers' pedagogy, learning mathematics can also be influenced by learners' attitudes and behavior towards the subject. Based on the study of Darmayanti et al. (2023), students' attitudes are described as "too soft attitudes-very difficult-bored-in a good way." Low study motivation, inability to comprehend the teacher's subject, and laziness when doing homework regularly. Moreover, the instructor's lack of proficiency in both the classroom and the subject matter was taught. These attitudes significantly affect learners' mathematical competencies.

In this regard, the context of Grade 9 students is timely and relevant. Based on quarterly assessments, Grade 9 was found to have low achievement in mathematics. Moreover, another interview was conducted with students, and they confirmed that one of the reasons for the low scores in the subject was the unmastered competencies in grade 8. This led grade 12 researchers to assess grade 9 students' competency in Mathematics 8 using the most essential competencies (MELCs) designed for grade 8.

Significantly, this study aims to investigate the competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8. Whatever assessment be concluded in this study shall be the basis for teachers to design enhancement programs and intervention plans. Thus, this study covers the school year 2023-2024 at the Sto Niño High School, Tanjay City Division. Specifically, the researchers addressed the following questions.

Research Questions

1. What least learned competency or competencies in Mathematics 8 during the first quarter do grade 9 students have?
2. What least learned competency or competencies in Mathematics 8 during the second quarter do grade 9 students have?

3. What least learned competency or competencies in Mathematics 8 during the third quarter do grade 9 students have?
4. What least learned competency or competencies in Mathematics 8 during the fourth quarter do grade 9 students have?
5. What quarter revealed the lowest composite mean?
6. How competent are Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8?
7. Based on the study's results, what recommendations can be made?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, locale, participants, instrument, and data-gathering procedures in the study.

Research Design

Any study must have a strong research design because it establishes the framework for the entire investigation. To address the research questions, it entails arranging and preparing the techniques and processes that will be applied to data collection and analysis. validity, and reliability of the findings are guaranteed by a well-designed research project. In this manner, the study is a quantitative approach utilizing descriptive statistics to describe how competent grade 9 students are in Mathematics 8 at Sto Niño High School, school year 2023-2024. This leads researchers to compile and arrange the attributes of a dataset. A group of observations or answers from a sample or complete population is called a dataset (Bhandari, 2023).

Research Locale

The location of research is essential to any study's success. The quality and dependability of the research findings can be significantly impacted by the location of the study. Carefully weighing several aspects, including accessibility, relevance to the study topic, and resource availability, is necessary when choosing a suitable research location. Relevantly, the researchers focused on Sto Niño High School as the core environment of the study. This is because the concentration of the study focused on the Grade 9 students' competence in Mathematics 8 in the school year 2023-2024.

Research Participants

Research participants are essential to the field of science. These people give freely of their time and energy to further knowledge and comprehension in a variety of academic subjects. It would not have been feasible to make many significant discoveries and advancements without their willingness to participate in research investigations. With the objectivity of the researchers, all Grade 9 students were purposively selected as participants based on the criteria set by the researchers. Purposive sampling is a deliberate and methodical selection process that employs samples to investigate particular qualities (Bisht, 2024).

Research Instrument

A vital tool in the process of obtaining data and information for research objectives are research instruments. These tools can be surveys, questionnaires, interviews, experiments, and observations, among other formats. Every tool is made to gather particular kinds of information that are pertinent to the current study subject. In this study, the researchers utilized a standardized learning competency tool taken from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) designed for Grade 8 students. This is to make sure that the tool used is valid has undergone thorough evaluation and is ready to use for academic endeavors.

Data Gathering Procedures

Procedures for collecting data are crucial to any research project because they lay the groundwork for outcomes interpretation and analysis. Data can be gathered using a variety of techniques, and methods to substantiate a study. Relevantly, in this study, the researcher employed a tripartite procedure namely, before data gathering, during data gathering, and after data gathering. Before data gathering, the researchers established criteria for the selection of the participants to have an objective sampling strategy. Moreover, ethical considerations were strictly observed by the participants including sending a permission letter to the school head of Sto Niño High School, then endorsed to the school's division superintendent of Tanjay City Division. Participants were also invited by the researchers for an orientation highlighting the purpose and significance of the study. Also, the researchers clearly emphasized the informed consent that participants were not forced to participate and could withdraw anytime they wished from the study. During the collection of data, researchers administered the survey questionnaire in the Grade 9 classroom as they preferred it. After the collection of data, the researchers tallied the result using the 5-point Likert scale and weighted mean to describe the competence of the Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8. It yielded an initial report which prompted the researchers to interview some of the students for the focus group discussion. This was to substantiate the competence level of the participants by eliciting their sentiments. Furthermore, the researchers had a pledge that the data gathered in the study would be kept with utmost confidentiality.

RESULTS

This section presents the data gathered for this study. This revealed the least competencies per quarter and the overall competence level of the Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 at Sto Niño High School, school year 2023-2024.

Table 1. Grade 9 students' level of competence in Mathematics 8 in the First Quarter

Competencies	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Factors completely different type of polynomials (polynomials with common monomial factor, difference of two squares, sum and difference of two cubes, perfect square trinomial, and general trinomials).	2.83	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving factors of polynomials.	2.83	Moderately Competent
Simplifies rational algebraic expressions.	2.53	Moderately Competent
Performs operations on rational algebraic expressions.	2.5	Slightly Competent
Solves problems involving rational algebraic expressions.	2.7	Moderately Competent
Illustrates the rectangular coordinates system and its issues.	2.66	Moderately Competent
Illustrates linear equations in two variables.	2.93	Moderately Competent
Illustrate and find the slope of a line given two points, equation, and graph.	2.93	Moderately Competent
Write the linear equation $ax + by = c$ in the form $y = mx + b$ and vice versa.	2.8	Moderately Competent
Graph a linear equation given (a) any two points; (b) the x – and y – intercepts; (c) the slope and a point on the line.	2.96	Moderately Competent
Describes the graph of a linear equation in terms of its intercepts and slope.	2.8	Moderately Competent
Describes the graph of a linear equation in terms of its intercepts and slope.	3.03	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving linear equations in two variables.	3.1	Moderately Competent
Illustrates a system of linear equations in two variables.	2.33	Slightly Competent
Graph a system of linear equations in two variables.	2.8	Moderately Competent
Categories when a given system of linear equations in two variables has graphs that are parallel, intersecting, and coinciding.	2.86	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables by (a) graphing; (b) substitution; (c) elimination	2.6	Slightly Competent
Composite Mean	2.77	Moderately Competent

Verbal Description

4.21-5.00 - Highly Competent
1.81-2.60 - Slightly Competent

3.41-4.20 - Competent
1.00-1.80 - Not Competent

2.61-3.40 - Moderately Competent

Table 1 shows that Grade 9 students were slightly competent in some competencies in Mathematics 8 in the first quarter. It was evident that illustrating a system of linear equations in two variables as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 2.33, performing operations on rational algebraic expressions which is 2.5 and 2.6 for Solving problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables by (a) graphing; (b) substitution; (c) elimination are the least learned competencies by the participants. On the other hand, students were moderately competent in describing the graphs of a linear equation in terms of their intercepts and slopes, as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 3.3. Moreover, being competent or highly competent is not evident in this table. Thus, Grade 9 students' competence level in Mathematics 8 is Moderately Competent, as shown by the composite mean of 2.77. Based on the interview conducted by the researchers, participants expounded that they found difficulties in learning the competency because they were not motivated in the subject due to some reasons, teachers' pedagogical approaches, pandemic times due to limited face-to-face classes, and their interest in the subject.

Table 2. Grade 9 Students' Level of Competence in Mathematics 8 in the Second Quarter

Competencies	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Differentiates linear inequalities in two variables from linear equations in two variables.	2.93	Moderately Competent
Illustrates and graphs linear inequalities in two variables.	2.96	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving linear inequalities in two variables.	3.03	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables.	2.6	Slightly Competent
Illustrates a relation and a function.	2.56	Slightly Competent
Verifies if a given relation, is a function.	3.3	Moderately Competent
Determines dependent and independent variables.	2.73	Moderately Competent
Finds the domain and range of a function.	3.00	Moderately Competent
Graph and illustrate linear functions and their (a) domain; (b) range; (c) table of values; (d) intercepts; and (e) slope.	3.26	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving linear functions.	3.06	Moderately Competent
Determines the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement.	2.96	Moderately Competent
Illustrates the equivalences of: (a) the statement and its contrapositive; and (b) the converse and inverse of a statement.	2.7	Moderately Competent
Uses inductive or deductive reasoning in an argument.	2.86	Moderately Competent
Writes a proof (both direct and indirect).	2.63	Moderately Competent
Composite Mean	2.89	Moderately Competent

Verbal Description

4.21-5.00 - Highly Competent 3.41-4.20 - Competent 2.61-3.40 - Moderately Competent
 1.81-2.60 - Slightly Competent 1.00-1.80 - Not Competent

The table shows the two least-learned competencies grade 9 students obtained. They were slightly competent in illustrating a relation and a function which was demonstrated by the weight of 2.56 and 2.6 for solving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables. On the contrary, students had the highest moderate competence in graphing and illustrating linear functions and their (a) domain, (b) range, (c) table of values, (d) intercepts, and (e) slope, which is demonstrated by the weighted mean of 3.26. Furthermore, this table does not show competence or high competence in Mathematics 8. Thus, the general competence of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 is Moderately Competent, substantiated by the weighted mean of 2.89.

Table 3. Grade 9 Students' Level of Competence in Mathematics 8 in the Third Quarter

Competencies	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Describes a mathematical system.	3.26	Moderately Competent
Illustrates the need for an axiomatic structure of a mathematical system in general, and in Geometry in particular: (a) defined terms; (b) undefined terms; (c) postulates; and (d) theorems.	3.43	Competent
Illustrates triangle congruence.	2.96	Moderately Competent
Illustrates the SAS, ASA and SSS congruence postulates.	3.76	Competent
Solves corresponding parts of congruent triangles.	3.36	Moderately Competent
Proves two triangles are congruent.	3.13	Moderately Competent
Proves statements on triangle congruence.	2.96	Moderately Competent
Applies triangle congruence to construct perpendicular lines and angle bisectors.	3.3	Moderately Competent
Composite Mean	3.27	Moderately Competent

Verbal Description

4.21-5.00 - Highly Competent 3.41-4.20 - Competent 2.61-3.40 - Moderately Competent
 1.81-2.60 - Slightly Competent 1.00-1.80 - Not Competent

The table revealed that Grade 9 students were moderately competent in most of the competencies in Mathematics 8 for the third quarter and two competencies that students demonstrated competence. Having 2.96 as a weighted means for the two competencies namely, illustrating triangle congruence, and proving statements on triangle congruence denotes that they are moderately competent. By contrast, in illustrating the need for an axiomatic structure of a mathematical system in general, and in Geometry in particular: (a) defined terms; (b) undefined terms; (c) postulates; and (d) theorems as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 3.43 was described as competent. Thus, the general competence of Grade 9 students in Math 8 is Moderately Competent, as demonstrated by the composite mean of 3.27, since there were no manifestations of competence and high competence shown in the table.

Table 4. Grade 9 Students' Level of Competence in Mathematics 8 in the Fourth Quarter

Competencies	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Illustrates theorems on triangle inequalities (Exterior Angle inequality Theorem, Triangle Inequality Theorem, Hinge Theorem).	3.36	Moderately Competent
Applies theorems on triangle inequalities.	4.06	Competent
Proves inequalities in a triangle.	3.1	Moderately Competent
Prove properties of parallel lines cut by a transversal.	3.33	Moderately Competent
Determines the conditions under which lines and segments are parallel or perpendicular.	3.00	Moderately Competent
Illustrates an experiment, outcome, sample space, and events.	3.06	Moderately Competent
Counts the number of occurrences of an outcome in an experiment: (a) table; (b) tree diagram; (c) systematic listing; and (d) fundamental counting principle.	3.16	Moderately Competent
Illustrates an experimental probability and a theoretical probability.	2.9	Moderately Competent
Solves problems involving probabilities of simple events.	3.13	Moderately Competent
Composite Mean	3.03	Moderately Competent
Verbal Description		
4.21-5.00 - Highly Competent	3.41-4.20 - Competent	2.61-3.40 - Moderately Competent
1.81-2.60 - Slightly Competent	1.00-1.80 - Not Competent	

The table above shows that Grade 9 students were moderately competent in most of the competencies in Math 8 in the last quarter. Students received the least learned competency in illustrating experimental probability and theoretical probability, as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 2.9. This means that the participants still need to improve the moderate competence they exhibited based on the results. Surprisingly, only one competency in Grade 9 students was competent. This competency concerns applying theorems on triangle inequalities, which is supported by the weighted mean of 4.06. Thus, the general competence level of grade students in Mathematics 8 competencies was moderately competent. This was even supported by the participants' sentiments for obtaining the highest competence in Grade 8 Mathematics. According to them, this was the time when they were able to understand the concept and they had background knowledge of the competency. Moreover, this competency was emphasized more by the Math Teacher during that time. Moreover, they found themselves moderately competent on the majority of the competencies in Mathematics 8.

Table 5. Overall Competence Level of Grade 9 Students in Mathematics 8

Quarters	Composite Mean	Verbal description
First quarter	2.77	Moderately Competent
Second quarter	2.89	Moderately Competent
Third quarter	3.27	Moderately Competent
Fourth quarter	3.03	Moderately Competent
Overall Composite Mean	2.99	Moderately Competent

Verbal Description
 4.21-5.00 - Highly Competent 3.41-4.20 - Competent 2.61-3.40 - Moderately Competent
 1.81-2.60 - Slightly Competent 1.00-1.80 - Not Competent

Table 5 shows the overall competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 competencies. It reveals that the first quarter was the most challenging among the four quarters in Math 8, as demonstrated by the composite mean of 2.77, which can be categorized as moderately competent. On the other hand, the fourth quarter had the highest composite mean of 3.03, indicating that students were moderately competent. As an overall competence level, the table shows 2.99 as the overall composite mean, which means that the general competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 competencies in all quarters is moderately competent.

DISCUSSION

This section provides a thorough discussion of the results obtained. It starts with Table 1, which is labeled as Grade 9 students' level of competence in Mathematics 8 in the First Quarter. This revealed that students were slightly competent in some competencies like illustrating a system of linear equations in two variables as demonstrated by the weighted mean of 2.33, performing operations on rational algebraic expressions which is 2.5 and 2.6 for Solving problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables by (a) graphing; (b) substitution; (c) elimination. In the second quarter, students were found to be slightly competent in illustrating a relation and a function which obtained a weighted of 2.56 and 2.6 for solving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables. Moreover, in the third quarter, Grade 9 students achieved a moderate competence level in two competencies, namely, illustrating triangle congruence and proving statements on triangle congruence, which is represented by a weighted mean of 2.96. Finally, in the fourth quarter, Students show an incredible difference since they exhibited competence in applying theorems to triangle inequalities, which is demonstrated by the weighted mean of 4.06. Furthermore, the general competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 is moderately competent, as represented by the overall composite mean of 2.99. This indicates that students are still unmastered and the least learned competencies in mathematics 8. Based on the interviews conducted by the researchers, the participants shared their sentiments regarding the subject. As expressed by the participants, *"It's hard for me since I do not have any books and other gadgets like cellphones and laptops or Internet connections in our place. I cannot study at home."* (P1). This was supported by a study by Torres (2024), which found that a lack of resources can affect students' academic achievement. This is

just one of the many factors that explain the competence level of Grade 9 students. Another participant said, 'I do not like math sir. It keeps me brother sometimes because there are lots of problems to solve and I did not know how to do it.' (P6). Moreover, "Sometimes, I can understand our teacher, but there are times also that I do not. Although I appreciate the way he teaches us, it could have been better if he had applied another teaching strategy. Sometimes, I get bored" (P3). These are some of the statements of the participants that serve as factors contributing to their low competence in mathematics 8.

Conclusions

The study concluded that Grade 9 students had the least learned competencies in Mathematics 8 from the first quarter to the fourth. In the first quarter, the students were slightly competent in illustrating a system of linear equations in two variables, performing operations on rational algebraic expressions, and solving problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables: (a) graphing, (b) substitution, and (c) elimination. Students' proficiency in demonstrating a relation and function, and in resolving problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables, was determined to be slightly competent in the second quarter. In the third quarter, Grade 9 students demonstrated a moderate degree of competency in two areas: proving statements about triangle congruence and illustrating triangle congruence. Lastly, in the fourth quarter, students indicated competence in applying theorems to triangle inequalities. This leads to the point that students had the lowest least-learned competencies in the first quarter. Thus, the general competence level of Grade 9 students in Mathematics 8 was moderately competent. The results of this study are also substantiated by the statements of the participants, who emphasized factors that may affect their competence in mathematics 8. One of these reasons is the lack of resources, as these learners are situated in the hinterland. In addition, their attitude and behavior toward the subject is another factor that demonstrates their slight competence in the subject. In addition, the teacher's pedagogical approach and knowledge affect grade 9 learners' motivation towards the subject.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the researchers suggest the following: (a) Mathematics teachers should be equipped with knowledge and pedagogy to sustain a motivating learning environment for learners. Participating in workshops and other relevant pieces of training and collaborative work among co-teachers and colleagues. Anent, (b) teachers shall also make initiatives like intervention plans and enhancement programs to improve the least learned competencies in Mathematics 8. This will provide avenues for learners to improve especially the competencies which are found to be slightly competent. (c) teachers also need to have a regular assessment and monitoring to gauge the competence level among learners to maximize the time for teaching and learning and for future researchers to and (d) use another technique or design. Using the correlation method can explicitly explain associations and relationships among chosen variables in the future study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

We, the researchers, Jinky F. Endab, Sunshine C. Calendario, Princess C. Colongon, and Rizame C. Colancolan, Anamie C. Casipong, and Joseph L. Torres authors of this study hereby declare that the implementation of the study took a careful and ethical approach. Before the actual implementation of the study, the researchers sent a permission letter to the school's division office for approval. After being approved, the researchers invited the possible participants for an orientation. The agenda included the nature and the purpose of the study, informed consent, the anonymity of the participants, the confidentiality of the data, and the freedom to withdraw. All of these were explained well and understood by the would-be participants. Consequently, the participants gave their support and signed the informed consent. Furthermore, the study is not plagiarized, and the sources cited in this paper are properly acknowledged. Also, the authors hereby allow the editorial board of this journal to make necessary changes for the betterment of the paper and final publication.

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